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Gathering Intelligence for Robust Crisis Governance: A Literature Review and Research Agenda

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ABSTRACT

The COVID-19 crisis has highlighted the critical role and challenges of information processing during turbulent times. While expert knowledge can reassure citizens, it may also seem exclusive, and government communication often risks being overwhelming or unclear. These dynamics underscore the complex relationship between information and crisis governance—a timely topic for renewed examination. This paper reviews literature at the intersection of information processing, knowledge management, and crisis governance to guide future research with heightened awareness of contemporary challenges. It critically examines existing work and identifies three key issues: the strategic production and use of knowledge, managing uncertainty, and fostering learning. The paper also explores how knowledge exchanges are enacted in practice and proposes directions for further study.

1 | Introduction

The COVID-19 crisis has once again shed light on the crucial role played by information and its processing in turbulent times. Policymakers at various levels of governance were seeking advice from experts, trying to make the best decisions possible under conditions of high uncertainty and time pressure (Deverell 2010, 2022). This was a clear attempt at managing the information asymmetry brought about by the crisis (Philipps et al. 2023)—but one must be careful about over-relying on expert advice, an approach that runs the risk of increasing uncertainty instead of reducing it (Fazey et al. 2013).

The volume of the information, the channels used, the language and justifications employed can in fact be experienced as unclear or confusing, thus at times missing the goal of supporting citizens' sense-making of the crisis and everyday decision-making. In both normal and turbulent times, each actor in society is making daily decisions on, for example, risk

assessment, compliance, information processing, and knowledge exchange.

At the basis of all these recognizable dynamics is the relationship between information and crisis governance, one that at this point in time is very relevant to review. Relevant literature acknowledges in fact multiple gaps: it is not yet clear how organizations address information asymmetry (Philipps et al. 2023), nor under which conditions interfaces for knowledge exchange take place (Van Enst et al. 2014). In addition, citizens cannot be considered in these dynamics just the recipients of policy measures, but an actor in themselves that needs to be included in a triangular interaction with science and policymakers (Bäckstrand 2003).

There is thus a need to delve further into this triangle, and this paper has the aim of reviewing the literature at the intersection of information processing, knowledge management, and crisis governance to pave the way for new research in this area of

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study with a renewed awareness of the challenges brought about by today's turbulent times.

Such times call for adaptation and innovation while preserving essential functions, goals, and values—what has been described as robust governance (Ansell et al. 2021, 2023). Constructing a societal intelligence is a central element of the robust governance approach, pointing at the potential of knowledge exchange practices where cognitive and political negotiation are facilitated, solutions expand, and co-creation is supported (Torfing et al. 2025).

Embracing this understanding of the relation between information, intelligence, and crisis, this study asks the question: *Through which lenses can intelligence for crisis governance be theoretically and empirically studied?* The contribution this paper aims at is threefold. First, it critically discusses the state-of-the-art building the knowledge in this field. Second, it identifies three challenges present in the scholarly work at this intersection: the strategic use and production of knowledge, uncertainty, and learning. Finally, it reviews how knowledge exchanges can be studied on the ground, suggesting avenues for further research. A surprisingly wide array of academic disciplines contributes to these goals, including international public administration, crisis management, risk regulation, public relations, clinical neuroscience, social epistemology, public management, business strategy, philosophy, and environmental policy.

The paper unfolds as follows. First, the research strategy is presented in detail. Then, the literature is reviewed, contextualizing information processing, knowledge management, and knowledge exchange within turbulent times. This section also explores how building intelligence can be seen as a social and epistemic activity. Following, the three main challenges are discussed. The successive section delves into knowledge interfaces as a way of building intelligence on the ground. Finally, a research agenda is presented together with the concluding remarks.

2 | Research Strategy

To delve deeper into the relationship between information and crisis governance and discover the overlaps in the literature between the two, this paper relies on a wide range of sources coming from diverse disciplines. This section will present the research strategy followed, justifying the selection choices made and how this led to the current analysis.

2.1 | A Narrative Review

First, it is important to underline that this literature review can be characterized as a *narrative* review. This type of review, among the most common, aims at generating understanding and has a wide-ranging scope. Given the inductive approach followed, the process of incremental discovery, and the flexibility needed regarding the boundaries of the subject of study, such a type of literature review fits the objectives of this study best (Bryman 2012).

This type of review allows to synthesize multiple points of view and new perspectives on the subject, providing an interpretation and critique of the current state of the art (Sukhera 2022). This is especially important as it matches the interpretivist epistemology of the author. However, a narrative review might be framed as nonsystematic and lacking methodological rigor (KU Leuven Bibliotheken 2024). To circumscribe these limitations, the following sub-sections elaborate on the search criteria and process of selection of the articles used.

2.2 | Keywords Search and Refinement

The starting point of the research was identifying the main keywords to be used later on in the search on bibliometric databases. The central concepts of this study are “information” and “crisis governance.” Some considerations are due for both. First, regarding “information,” the goal of this study is understanding the dynamics surrounding the use and processing of information during turbulent times. This carries some implications. First, it became clear that “information” in itself would not be useful as a keyword for the current purposes. On the contrary, other closely related concepts would allow for the inclusion of relevant sources. Following the framework by Ackoff (1989)—also discussed later in this paper—concepts such as “knowledge” and “intelligence” were included as potential keyword options, as they are understood as what information transforms into when employed in a system.

Moving onto “crisis governance,” both terms were employed singularly in a first trial bibliometric search together with “information.” From this attempt, it became clear that the combination “information governance” as an AND search did not issue relevant results. Thus, “crisis” remained in the keyword options. In addition, through this inductive process, it was apparent that the way *organizations* and their interplay with information use had been quite extensively researched and could be useful to study different levels of governments in similar knowledge demand and supply needs.

Based on these incremental discoveries and insights, the final keyword search included the following:

- Intelligence;
- Information AND crisis;
- Information AND processing AND crisis;
- Organization AND knowledge.

These keywords were then employed on different online bibliometric databases: JStor, Taylor & Francis, and Wiley Online Library. These overlapping searches made sure no items were being overlooked. The results were shown per relevance and not filtered per journal nor subject to adhere to the goals of the research. The results were first screened based on their title, and then on their abstract. In the case of the keyword “intelligence” this was a way to eliminate from the search all the literature related to secret information and agents and retain the one referring to a cognitive ability.

FIGURE 1 | Process for the selection of publications.

2.3 | Final Sources Selection and Further Snowballing

The sources included for the final analysis included circa 60 publications, including books, book chapters, journal articles, and encyclopedia entries. This literature belongs to the following wide range of disciplines: international public administration, crisis management, risk regulation, public relations, clinical neuroscience, social epistemology, public management, business strategy, philosophy, and environmental policy.

While going through the relevant selected publications, some additional sources were discovered through the citations made by the authors. Such items were also screened and then, if relevant, added to the library supporting the development of this study. At the same time, publications were also excluded if they did not prove to be significant to answer the research question of this paper when reading them in full. Finally, the preliminary results of this analysis were also presented at an international conference, which helped give direction and support the relevance of this study project (Figure 1).

3 | Studying Intelligence for Crisis Governance: Theoretical Approaches

This section presents the available theoretical lenses through which intelligence for crisis governance can be studied. These approaches are grounded in the concepts of “information” and “knowledge,” which are often used in the literature either interchangeable or in combination with other terms. An initial relevant differentiation comes from Ackoff (1989), according to whom structured data becomes information, contextualized information becomes knowledge, and applying knowledge to a situation constitutes intelligence (in De Angelis 2013, 807–808). As this review is interested in intelligence for crisis governance, it is thus important to focus on the level where decisions are made, which is thus knowledge application, that is, intelligence (De Angelis 2013). Information by itself can in fact stay passive (Hallin 2023) and it is through translating and applying knowledge that policies develop (Iyalomhe et al. 2013). We thus need to evolve from a knowledge society paradigm to a collective intelligence society (Hallin 2023).

Based on this understanding of information, knowledge, and intelligence, the following sub-sections distinguish between information processing, knowledge management, knowledge

exchange, and intelligence as epistemic activity as relevant theoretical approaches to study intelligence for crisis governance.

3.1 | Information Processing

Contemporary crises bring about varying degrees of information asymmetry, where the information available is insufficient or too ambiguous to perform tasks. To address such uncertainty and equivocality, information processing is a relevant concept. In particular, organizational information-processing theory, which aims to reduce uncertainty and manage equivocality for superior performance, is a theoretical approach that can offer useful insights.

Information processing is understood as the steps of gathering, interpreting, and transferring information (Dahmann and Roehrich 2019). Actors in the supply chain can improve performance and foster learning by collaborative engagement, where both upstream and downstream partners of the supply chain are included.

Such information flows provide opportunities for learning within organizations and improve performance through collaborative engagement among actors and organizations in the supply chain.

The effective sharing of information, skills, and resources is crucial for organizations to face crisis induced uncertainty (Phillips et al. 2023). While the literature clarifies that there is limited capacity to address uncertainty fully and tackling equivocality, information flows within collaborative engagement still have the potential of turning that knowledge into intelligence and shaping innovative crisis responses. Philipps et al. (2023) argues that this “reciprocal transfer of information” is crucial for a “rapid and effective innovative response.” Analogously, Bourgon (2009) underlines the need for flexibility, information, and knowledge sharing. She adds that citizens and other actors—beyond policymakers—possess different views and valuable information that shape innovative responses. The pooling of diverse knowledge types would in fact expand the crises solutions available and facilitate the early detection of problems within policy measures and their implementation (Torfing et al. 2025).

3.2 | Knowledge Management

Knowledge management as a theoretical approach addresses the issue of recognizing and including different perspectives. Authors emphasize that issue framing stems from promoting certain types of knowledge and “dominant disciplinary framings” (Hoppe et al. 2013, 290). For example, in the COVID-19 crisis, disciplines like epidemiology were dominating the crisis governance during the first wave of the pandemic, creating an epistemological hierarchy.

Literature within knowledge management also discusses the distinction between explicit and tacit knowledge. On the one hand, explicit knowledge can be easily transferred, for example,

TABLE 1 | Ideal models of knowledge production.

Ideal models of knowledge production	
Linear model	Scientists as separate from society; trustworthy, capable, and responsible for producing knowledge that leads society forward.
Relational model	Actors outside of science possess vital knowledge and play prominent roles in knowledge production. Experiences of practitioners are incorporated on an ongoing basis.
Emergent model	Absence of a central moderator or facilitator; actors and interfaces are unspecified. Knowledge that emerges from chaotic and unscripted interactions is sometimes weakly supported by evidence.

Source: Adapted from Gustafsson et al. (2017).

via presentations or guidelines (Platts and Yeung 2000). The advantages of this in times of crisis are clear, as it allows swift and summarized communication. Platts and Yeung (2000, 349) call this the “management approach,” aligning with the new public management focus on performance standards, results, measurement, and monitoring. On the other hand, this positivist view of knowledge is contrasted with a subjective perspective that recognizes different knowledge types (Pütz and Brassel 2021). Tacit knowledge is “personal, context-specific, and hard to formalize and communicate” (Bordum 2002, 51). It includes personal experiences, intuitions, ideas, and emotions (see Polanyi 1966). These diverse perspectives and experiences would support crisis governance that matches citizens’ needs, but the Western scientific, reductionist view of knowledge favors and legitimizes explicit knowledge (Platts and Yeung 2000).

Gustafsson et al. (2017) connects this debate to practice, emphasizing the importance of understanding how different knowledge types contribute to change. Their research introduces three models of knowledge production: the classical linear model, the relational model, and the emergent model (Table 1). They argue that the emergent model best captures the engagement of diverse perspectives from multiple actors impacting decision-making.

This contribution opens the theoretical space for the cohabitation of explicit and tacit knowledge, which De Angelis (2013) discusses more directly. He defines knowledge management (KM) as “a set of practices aimed at the interaction between tacit and explicit knowledge” (p. 808). Through these practices, organizations can act intelligently, developing new competencies.

3.3 | Knowledge Exchange

Knowledge exchange is defined as “processes of generating, sharing, and/or using knowledge through various methods appropriate to the context, purpose, and participants involved” and includes concepts like coproduction, generation, and brokerage (Fazey et al. 2013, 19; Pütz and Brassel 2021, 166). This theoretical lens allows to study the iterative process of sharing knowledge with others, tackling knowledge production from a more critical perspective.

Knowledge exchange can in fact be understood as a process of empowerment, where actors make a conscious decision to share knowledge—an action entangled in power dynamics (Fazey et al. 2013). Within such process, participants might feel their identity more or less validated, and the potential for conflict arises.

This is where coproduction of knowledge comes in. Knowledge coproduction has been on the rise within the literature (Bird 2014; Fazey et al. 2013; Gustafsson et al. 2017; Hoppe et al. 2013; Pütz and Brassel 2021; Van Enst et al. 2014). Authors argue it can reduce the potential for conflict (Fazey et al. 2013), but also foster collective action (Bourgon 2009). This is particularly important in times of crisis, as showed by Liu and Lin (2023) in their case study on deliberative policymaking during COVID-19 in Taiwan. Following some protests and success stories of open-government movements, the Taiwanese government funded in 2014 an open consultation platform called *vTaiwan*. Through this platform, the public is involved in four phases: brainstorming, preference expression, deliberation, and institution. Letting people set the agenda on issues that concern them enhances how much they value the outcomes and ultimately the resilience of society in the face of the pandemic.

However, these arguments do not come without challenging questions. Is it possible, or desirable, to include citizens in processes of knowledge production, validation, and application? Shall we include lay knowledge in risk assessments? Isn’t uncertainty to be reduced through scientific knowledge championed by experts? Bäckstrand (2003) righteously asks, connecting this debate to the themes of explicit and implicit knowledge from knowledge management. Naustdalslid (2011) answer would be that “science can develop scientific solutions” which then are applied to societal problems. In this sense, as direct recipient of, for example, crisis containment measures, society cannot be left out of these processes.

It is though important to stay grounded to the crisis reality, where time pressure is high and coproduction might look unrealistic to policymakers. When it comes to cognitive diversity, there are in fact diminishing returns after a certain threshold of adding more people to the conversation (Landemore 2012b). The solution seems to lie in what Landemore (2012a) calls “collective wisdom.” This can be achieved both through deliberative practices of knowledge

exchange and aggregation procedures that “do not require actual communication or an exchange of views among the participants” (p. 5).

3.4 | Intelligence as a Social and Epistemic Activity

Philosophy of science, and more specifically epistemology, are an additional theoretical approach to study intelligence for crisis governance. Epistemology deals with knowledge validity, its limits, and methods. Different disciplines or groups possess in fact different epistemologies and employ different methods to make sense of information and create knowledge.

Sternberg (2012) affirms that intelligence is a social activity and, because it involves the production of knowledge, it is also an epistemic one. Multiple scholars argue for the need to incorporate additional factors into policymaking other than scientific evidence, such as social interests and local knowledge, or more broadly the perspectives of those affected by the issue at hand (Bäckstrand 2003; Naustdalslid 2011; Thompson et al. 2022; Pütz and Brassel 2021).

Additional authors clarify why this inclusion is crucial from an epistemological point of view. If we consider the ways through which individuals get to know something, this is a finite list. These are authority, habit of thought, rationalism, and empiricism (Bruce 2008, 172). Science is also mentioned as a fifth way that combines both rationalism and empiricism. In the case of crisis governance, crisis communication often relies on authority, where there is a complete dependence on the source of information, which is more authoritative than who is communicating the knowledge. An illustration is a policymaker referring to expert knowledge and advice when communicating a new crisis measure. In this case, citizens cannot access how the knowledge was created in the first place and cannot see the logic behind it. In other words, the epistemology according to which this knowledge was produced is not available to the users. Andler (2012) agrees with this point, arguing that what often “gets in the way” is that actors do not have access to the reasons of others, thus hindering the production of intelligence. This also happens between the worlds of science and policy, which possess heterogeneous paradigms and thus struggle to understand each other’s epistemologies, hindering the potential of knowledge exchange (Iyalomhe et al. 2013; Thompson et al. 2022; Pütz and Brassel 2021).

Crises create the need for knowledge that is “credible, salient, and legitimate” (Van Enst et al. 2014, 11). If there is no consensus on what constitutes relevant norms and values, this will contribute to making problems even more unstructured. For example, prioritizing security versus human rights in crisis governance will bring different consensus when it comes to crisis measures.

Thus, seeing intelligence as a social and epistemological activity allows to study the misunderstandings between different groups, and explain what might hamper effective action in times of crisis. This approach also makes clear that there exist competing models of knowledge-making in the world and that

science is not universally accepted as authoritative (Hoppe et al. 2013). Thus, how to solve this mismatch between knowledge demand and supply within crisis governance?

Dinesh (2023) presents a case on the “Smarter Crowdsourcing in the Age of Coronavirus” initiative, launched by various partners including TheGovLab at the beginning of the pandemic. Unlike common crowdsourcing efforts, Smarter Crowdsourcing is a methodology that not only brings a large number of people together to create knowledge—but also makes sure that expertise is diversified (both in discipline and language, country of origin) and brought together rapidly in times of crisis. This diverse expertise results in more innovative ideas, capable of tackling global problems. Dinesh also underlines that expertise, in this case, was also considered to be found in lived experience, thus matching the arguments on the importance of tacit knowledge and drawing from different types of knowledge. Experts could directly communicate with institutions and policymakers through the organized sessions, providing an opportunity for their diverse paradigms to come closer together and fill that gap between knowledge demand and supply.

4 | Three Challenges to Gathering Intelligence for Crisis Governance

These theoretical approaches delineate the considerable impact the crisis context has on the relationship between information, knowledge, and intelligence. These create very specific challenges on all sides of knowledge supply and demand. The effective share of information becomes crucial to deal with information asymmetry (Philipps et al. 2023). At the same time, the demands on science change and crisis conditions are not ideal for making “good science” (Van Dooren and Noordegraaf 2020). The following sub-sections present the main challenges to gathering intelligence for crisis governance: the strategic use of knowledge and monopolization of the public discourse, the handling of uncertainty caused by information asymmetry and equivocality, and lastly crisis-induced learning.

4.1 | Strategic Use and Production of Knowledge

The strategic use and production of knowledge is a phenomenon taking place both on the side of policy and on the side of science (Van Enst et al. 2014). On the one hand, policymakers can indeed deliberately ignore certain bodies of knowledge or use knowledge in a selected way. This also happens through advisory committees, which according to Bäckstrand (2003) are highly intertwined with political processes. Similarly, Iyalomhe et al. (2013) claim that science’s input into policies could also be easily distorted by the norms and institutional settings of policymaking. On the other hand, scientists could also selectively present knowledge, produce incomplete accounts, and thus retain the position of “problem owners,” as defined by Naustdalslid (2011). According to this scholar, in an era where policymakers make an inflationary use of expert advice (Bäckstrand 2003), scientists are in this unique position to “speak truth to power” (Naustdalslid 2011, 250). In this sense,

Hoppe (2005) underlines that politics has paradoxically contributed to its own scientization.

However, there is also another side to this debate, and it touches upon consensus in the scientific community. Thompson et al. (2022) indeed claim that in the case of unsettled scientific debate, policymakers might ignore scientific input, which is usually deemed necessary to avoid policy failures (Baekkeskov and Öberg 2017). A consequence and risk of such circumstances is that there is pressure on experts to appear consensual, especially if there is time pressure in terms of policymaking. Baekkeskov and Öberg (2017) call this the “rally to the flag,” which would see scientists attempting to provide a timely response by presenting a unified front while hiding disagreements from the wider public. The authors also mention the media as contributing to this “rally” and biased selection of options by giving space in the news to experts who agree on a certain issue. The issue of exclusion of scientists who disagree with the dominant perspective is presented by Van Dooren and Noordegraaf (2020) as well in their research of “staging science” during COVID-19.

4.2 | Uncertainty: Challenging Traditional Science

However, in situations with high decision stakes and conflicting interests or implications, even (consensual) well-founded scientific knowledge might be rejected (Naustdalslid 2011). This is where the theme of uncertainty comes in. Pütz and Brassel (2021) argue that traditional science has been challenged: issues such as the environmental ones do indeed confront science with such conflicting values and deep uncertainties that multiple authors speak of post-normal science (Funtowicz and Ravetz 1993; Naustdalslid 2011). In their 1993 piece on “Science for the post-normal age,” Funtowicz and Ravetz claim that when facing this high level of systems uncertainties and decision stakes—which are their *x* and *y*—the applicable science is one including multiple legitimate perspectives, where it is not possible to retain full control and there is an assumption of unpredictability. The extension of the peer community in this framework includes everyone with a stake in the issue.

Thus, Funtowicz and Ravetz add this problem-solving strategy of post-normal science to the other two parts of their framework: applied science, and professional consultancy (Table 2). These strategies are complementary to each other: scientific and expert knowledge stays relevant, and professional consultancy provides support, but an additional layer might be necessary when it comes to such deep epistemological uncertainty. On the one hand, Van Dooren and Noordegraaf (2020) claim that we

are dependent on science for the reduction of uncertainty. On the other, Fazey et al. (2013) also add that over-relying on expert advice has paradoxically not reduced but increased the level of uncertainty. In this difficult balance, what we know from the COVID-19 case is that many European countries relied on professional consultancy—which makes the use of this framework still relevant today.

Newspapers such as POLITICO (Braun and De Villepin 2021) and The Guardian (Jolly and Syal 2020) have both published pieces on the role of consultants in supporting French and UK governments in delivering their public services, at a pace during the pandemic which caused some disbelief and shock by more conservative civil servants. POLITICO also highlights that indeed the UK, Spain, Germany, and Switzerland were also relying on consultancies and that this was not a new phenomenon at all. However, what seems unsettling is the increased frequency in recent years and the potential erosion of transparency and accountability. Given the challenges of turbulent times, consultancies supported governments working within time constraints and progressing much more rapidly on for example, the test-and-trace system, medicines, and protective equipment procurement, or more generally designing economic recovery plans. Section 5 will provide examples of interfaces also aiming at solving uncertainty at the epistemological level, by for example, including multiple stakeholders.

4.3 | Learning

When discussing information asymmetry and information-processing theory, Dahlmann and Roehrich (2019) also point out that information flows provide chances for organizational learning. Learning is another relevant issue when it comes to gathering intelligence, especially in the context of crisis governance. First, learning is present in multiple definitions of intelligence. As an illustration, Colom et al. (2010) include in their research various descriptions of what intelligence is, including learning quickly and learning from experience. The value of experience is reiterated by Sternberg (2012) in his article on intelligence in “Dialogues in clinical neuroscience.”

Turning to political science, the work of Deverell (2010, 2022) is particularly relevant. This author underlines the valuable input of organizational learning theory to explain the relationship between information, knowledge, organizational behavior, and change. Such change would concern both outcomes and states of knowledge—thus better understanding previous dynamics and successively acting accordingly. When it comes to policy change and learning, Hoppe (2005, 212) provides a pessimistic argument by underlining that this change is “threatened by the political inclination to try and the political constraint not to fail—and consequently the political inability to learn.” Despite this more negative account, Deverell provides multiple perspectives on learning processes.

Two interesting pairs of concepts are discussed in both of Deverell’s publications (2010, 2022) in this respect. The first is the distinctness between single- and double-loop learning. Single-loop learning involves routine changes and is aimed at preserving consistency and thus the stability of fundamental norms, values,

TABLE 2 | Uncertainty levels and solving strategies.

Level of uncertainty	Problem-solving strategy
Technical	Applied science
Methodological	Professional consultancy
Epistemological	Post-normal science

Source: Adapted from Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993).

and principles. In the case of double-loop learning, the fundamental norms and policies of the organization would also undergo change. This would thus represent a more radical learning process. The second pair of concepts is inter- and intra-crisis learning. The former takes place after the crisis, learning from it and enacting changes that would make the organization prepared for the next one. The latter happens within the crisis, thus aiming at improving the management capacity when uncertainties and stakes are at their highest. Additional interesting points made by Deverell (2022) are that learning in an organization is a social activity, and it is also something that citizens would expect from policymakers and authorities in the aftermath of a crisis. In his work, the idea also emerges that “it takes a second crisis to mobilize attention to the underlying problems” (Kingdon 2014 in Deverell 2022). Thus, one can deduce that crises do induce learning and Deverell highlights the need to research more about the relationship between organizational crisis management response and learning to build robust solutions.

5 | Studying Intelligence for Crisis Governance: Empirical Approaches

After discussing theoretical approaches and their challenges to studying intelligence for crisis governance, this section presents empirical approaches relevant to this study goal.

Thus, where do these knowledge interactions take place? Where is intelligence gathered and developed for crisis governance? The literature points at knowledge interfaces, as “social processes which encompass relations between scientists and other actors in the policy process, and which allow for exchanges, co-evolution, and joint construction of knowledge with the aim of enriching decision-making” (den van den Hove 2007, 815). Iyalomhe et al. (2013, 371) propose their definition, describing the science-policy interface as a “complex multi-level system of control and of knowledge production among a group of actors engaged in knowing and managing crucial environmental issues.” Finally, and deviating the most from other definitions, Hoppe et al. (2013, 284) define science-policy interactions from a macro-perspective as “ongoing co-productions between the scientization of politics and the politicization of science.”

Two elements are worth underlining regarding these definitions. First, the production of knowledge as a goal of such a social process of interaction and engagement is constantly present. Second, the literature focuses exclusively on the interface between science and politics (Pütz and Brassel 2021; Sarkki et al. 2015; Van Enst et al. 2014). While other actors are mentioned, the role foreseen for citizens is not clear in these conceptualizations. While this topic might be covered by other streams of scholarly output, such as citizen science (e.g., Günther et al. 2023; Shruti et al. 2022), this reinforces the argument made above that citizens are mostly perceived in the literature as passive recipients of policies and/or expert advice, thus being excluded from accessing antecedent epistemologies by which the knowledge was created (Andler 2012; Bruce 2008).

Despite this, some authors have discussed the importance of democratic participation, science co-creation, and seeing

science as a multi-party endeavor. For instance, Pütz and Brassel (2021) argue that science is transforming into a multi-party dialogue and employ the post-normal science conceptualization by Funtowicz and Ravetz (1993) in their research. Similarly, Clar and Steurer (2018) claim that tools provided to support policy making, for example, scientific advice in various forms, “must not ignore but build on the needs and capacities of target groups” (p. 179). There is indeed agreement in the literature that actors outside of science possess valuable knowledge, which can complement professional expertise (Bäckstrand 2003; Gustafsson et al. 2017) thus bridging the gap between what is happening locally and centrally (Phillips et al. 2023).

What further emerges from the literature on science-policy interfaces is that even these two worlds need bridging. Thompson et al. (2022) indeed underline that the effectiveness of this interface has been hampered by a lack of understanding between the paradigms and imperatives characterizing the two sides. Iyalomhe et al. (2013) define for this reason the interface between science and policy as ambiguous and they call for a revisiting of the relationship between science, end-users, and governance. They build up their point by discussing the need for translation of knowledge between science and policy. Pütz and Brassel (2021) illustrate this gap between the two worlds by arguing that there are different expectations about how knowledge is to be exchanged, thus making knowledge exchanges a challenging process. This is supported by Clar and Steurer (2018) who state that knowledge does not transfer easily between science and policymaking. When giving examples of barriers to such knowledge exchange, Pütz and Brassel (2021) mention the different epistemologies of science and policymaking—thus reiterating the previous argument about the lack of understanding of each other’s paradigms. The absence of interfaces is also presented in itself as a barrier to knowledge exchange, hence supporting the potential of such social processes.

Having critically presented the definitions, it is important to also present how interfaces could develop in practice. Authors have brought forward examples of civic science, communities of practice, and boundary organizations. These accounts will be here discussed together with the existing typologies of interfaces.

5.1 | Civic Science

According to Bäckstrand (2003), civic science includes both participation and representation and can be defined as “the efforts by scientists to reach out to the public, communicate scientific results and contribute to scientific literacy” (Clark and Illman 2001, 28). Thus, such an approach places civil society at the center of the scientific endeavor. In practice, examples include consensus conferences, participatory technology assessments, citizen juries, and public hearings.

Civic science as representation means solving the skewed representation in the current production of science, by for example, including marginalized groups. An interesting point made by Bäckstrand (2003) is that democratic participation in science is

mainly taking place at the domestic level and is more limited as far as, for example, scientific assessment is concerned. Thus, interesting cases to study civic science for crisis governance might be found within local governance. The REGROUP project has experimented with this approach, setting up five citizens' juries in different European countries to debate the intersection of scientific knowledge and democratic politics during COVID-19 (Leruth and Tortola 2025).

5.2 | Communities of Practice

Moving to communities of practice, these are referred to by Iyalomhe et al. (2013) as activities taking place in a certain social and historical context that structures the engagement of participants. Wenger et al. (2002) define this term as “a group of people who share a concern, a set of problems, or a passion about a subject matter, and who deepen their knowledge and expertise in this by interacting on an ongoing basis” (Iyalomhe et al. 2013, 371).

Such a community has the potential to allow interactions between different paradigms and thus knowledge types. In addition, the authors underline that in this context the participants also negotiate how useful and relevant the jointly accepted knowledge is Boucher et al. (2023) list communities of practice as a method to achieve one of the core functions of collective intelligence, that is, sense-making, learning, generating memory, and wisdom (Table 3).

The creation of jointly accepted knowledge is indeed among the potential goals of these activities, together with joint problem-solving and mutual learning. Hallin (2023) claims indeed that communities of practice in societies are illustrations of ways through which collective tacit knowledge is formed. Iyalomhe et al. (2013) also underline that such activities can take place within more formal organizations, such as a research project. Horizon Europe projects are an example thereof, bringing together scholars from different EU countries and collecting their insights based on both explicit and tacit knowledge.

5.3 | Boundary Organizations

Finally, Clar and Steurer (2018) and Hoppe (2005, 2013) have researched boundary organizations. Clar and Steurer (2018)

TABLE 3 | Core functions of collective intelligence.

Core functions of collective intelligence
Observing or gathering data
Modeling and predicting
Generating options
Filtering, deliberating, deciding
Implementing
Learning by making sense, remembering, synthesizing into wisdom

Source: Boucher et al. (2023).

maintain that the goal of boundary organizations is to facilitate two-way communication between science and policymaking. This can also be referred to as “knowledge brokerage” (Clar and Steurer 2018, 172). The authors also illustrate services provided by such an organization to reach that goal, such as policy analyses and evaluations, compilations of scientific data, standardized decision support tools, networking and consulting services, and public awareness activities.

Hoppe et al. (2013) provide further examples of “boundary objects,” such as indicator systems, econometric, models, and report series. Their work expands the scope of boundary work, to include not only quality assessment of scientific research but also for example, the design of innovative policy instruments or the evaluation of policy impacts. According to previous research by Hoppe (2005), boundary work fosters cognitive authority. Hoppe et al. (2013) cite the European Environmental Agency as a boundary organization at the EU level. Similarly, other EU agencies like the European Center for Disease Prevention and Control and the European Medicines Agency (EMA) were in the spotlight during the COVID-19 crisis (Müller and Fraussen 2024). Despite differences in formal powers, these bodies serve as interfaces among experts, citizens, and politicians, enabling knowledge exchange and intelligence gathering.

5.4 | Typologies: Science-Policy Engagement, Knowledge Exchange, Boundary Arrangements

First, Thompson et al. (2022) categorize science-policy engagement into three types based on the previous research of Cullen et al. (2001) and Van Enst et al. (2014). Their categorization (Table 4) thus includes engagement as purchaser provider (I), collaborative (IIa), participatory knowledge development (IIb), co-generative (IIc), and boundary organization (III). Related to the debates recognized until now in this review, the participatory knowledge development and the co-generative categories of science-policy engagement possess interesting features that could support the bridging between the two worlds, such as scientists partaking as mere participants and not initiators (IIb) or scientists working with policy to identify knowledge needs (IIc).

In terms of knowledge exchange, Pütz and Brassel (2021) present a five elements typology: knowledge transfer, knowledge transfer support, knowledge exchange, knowledge exchange support, and participatory knowledge development and use. In the categories including “support,” this implies the support by boundary organizations or knowledge advocates.

TABLE 4 | Models of science-policy engagement.

Models of engagement	
I	Purchaser provider
IIa	Collaborative
IIb	Participatory knowledge development
IIc	Co-generative
III	Boundary organization

Source: Thompson et al. (2022).

TABLE 5 | Models of boundary arrangements.

	Convergent logic	Divergent logic	Advocacy	Learning
Primacy of science	Technocracy	Enlightenment	Dispositional	Pure learning
Primacy of politics	Engineering	Bureaucracy	Adversarial	Coping

Source: Adapted from Hoppe (2005).

Relevant to this study project is category 5.1, denominated “coproduction of knowledge through participation.”

Lastly, Hoppe (2005) outlines eight models of boundary arrangements (Table 5), based on two axes: the primacy of science or politics, and whether the logic between them is convergent or divergent. From these emerge the enlightenment, technocracy, bureaucracy, and engineering models. The first two imply primacy for science, with technocracy embodying a convergent logic, that is, experts holding power. The latter two imply primacy for politics, with engineering embodying a convergent logic, that is, politicians retaining power and assigning detailed tasks to scientists as engineers. Hoppe (2005) also adds models based on advocacy (dispositional and adversarial) and learning (pure learning and coping).

Relevant to this study, the dispositional model views science advisors and policymakers as influencing political discourse, while science produces boundary objects like those illustrated above. The coping model, by contrast, represents the politicians' struggle presented in the section on learning - between the drive to change, the inclination to try, and the constraint not to fail, thus ultimately hindering learning.

6 | Discussion and Concluding Remarks

This review had the goal of answering the question: *Through which lenses can intelligence for crisis governance be theoretically and empirically studied?* By providing a critical discussion of both theoretical (Sections 3 and 4) and empirical (Section 5) approaches available, this review presents a useful reflection on the state of the art at the intersection of information processing, knowledge management, and crisis governance.

Such work has important implications for scholars working within these disciplines or at this interdisciplinary boundary. The theoretical approaches presented put in opposition concepts such as explicit and tacit knowledge, technocracy and deliberative democracy, effective sharing of information and information asymmetry, authority and coproduction, good science, and strategic use of knowledge. These dichotomies however often do not mirror our complex reality, made even more complex by crisis induced turbulence. There is thus a need not only to test these empirical approaches at different levels of governance, but also to explore the in-between, that is how these ideas co-exist in our crisis governance systems.

Turning to more specific suggestions for further research, first, it is not clear how organizations address information asymmetry and information processing throughout a crisis. Interfaces such as boundary organizations or communities of

practice might be involved in such processes, but the conditions under which interfaces take place are also not systematically researched. There is indeed no data on quality boundary work and what are the necessary and/or sufficient conditions for a certain interface to take place, to decline, to be substituted by another one, or by a certain configuration of interfaces. Thus, there is a need to look into these dynamics.

Furthermore, while there is consensus that traditional science is challenged by turbulence and that there are multiple legitimate perspectives to be included, how citizens can participate in the production, validation, and application of scientific knowledge is still to be understood. Within the post-normal science understanding, it is also necessary to develop guidelines for the organization of knowledge processes. In this context, it is also valuable to identify knowledge gatekeepers in different settings. Given the impact this has on knowledge exchange and thus on learning, it could also bring further light on why some individuals and organizations learn and reform and others do not. There is indeed a lack of empirical studies presenting examples of both inter and intra-crisis learning. Lastly, given the pressure to appear consensual, further research could also study the impact of experts on the range of policy options considered.

To conclude, some words on the limitations of this review. Starting from the methodology, this is a narrative review. While this had major advantages in terms of flexibility and autonomy for the author, this also implies less methodological rigor compared to a systematic review. However, Section 2 includes detailed information on the selection choices made, strengthening the review's transparency and reproducibility. In addition, regarding the sample of publications part of this review, one important point to underline is that many focus on environmental policy, environmental issues, and climate change. While this provides relevant illustrations for the research question at hand, it is an interesting finding that scholarly attention at this intersection has mostly focused on this policy field. Climate change as a creeping crisis with a clear epistemological hierarchy might have spurred experimentation with knowledge interfaces. In addition, this other streams of literature on for example, trust, network governance, and risk management were not covered in this review and can be used in further research to contextualize and control findings.

Conflicts of Interest

The author declares no conflicts of interest.

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